

Influence of Achievement Goals and Engagement on the Academic Performance of Senior High School Transfer Students

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Abstract:-Transferring to a new academic institution can be a challenging experience for students. This study determined the achievement goals and engagement and their influence on the academic performance of transfer students at Misamis University, Philippines. The quantitative study used the descriptive- correlational design in examining the relationship between academic goals and engagement to the academic performance of the respondents. The statistical tools used for the quantitative study were Mean, Standard deviation and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient in analyzing the quantitative data. The respondents included 269 students from the different strands of Senior High School Department of Misamis University, School Year 2019-2020. They were selected through stratified random sampling using lottery technique. Results revealed that the achievement goals of the transfer students were good while their engagement was high. The academic performance of the respondents was very satisfactory. The students' achievement goals as to mastery approach and the student's agentic engagement had an influence on the academic performance of the students. The study concludes that the goals and engagement of the students can have effects on their achievement in school. The institution needs to maintain the learning environment that ensure effective instruction and a smooth teaching-learning process.

Keywords:-Engagement, goals, involvement, performance, students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Achievement goals are self-regulatory commitments that provide direction to individuals as they recognize and respond to competence-relevant situations. There are four forms of achievement goals: Mastery-approach goals (mastering a task; improving over time), performance-approach goals (consistently outperforming others), mastery-avoidance goals (not short of mastering a task; not decline over time), and performance-avoidance goals (not outperformed by others) (Sommet & Elliot, 2016).

A study which examined the influence of achievement goals and scaffolding on self-regulated learning (SRL) and achievement within MetaTutor, revealed a significant interaction between achievement goals and condition on achievement outcomes, such that learners adopting a dominant performance-approach demonstrated higher achievement in the prompt and feedback state (Duffy & Azevedo, 2015). Moreover, a research which evaluated the relations between achievement goals, emotions, learning

strategies, and performance as informed by Pekrun's control-value theory of emotions illustrate the benefits of mastery-approach goals for students' emotions, with performance-approach goals predicting less critical thinking, and performance-avoidance goals predicting more anxiety, boredom, critical thinking, and lower achievement gains.

On the other hand, academic engagement refers to attention, class participation, and time-on-task, and it includes student engagement, school engagement, child engagement, and student participation (Metz, 2013). Academic engagement can be described as efforts devoted by students to academic activities, and it is a result of dynamic interactions between students, educators, academic activities, as well as educational conditions and environments (Ghasemi et al., 2018). Student engagement was a significant predictor of academic performance (Lee, 2014).

Moreover, some studies were found the significant differences in academic engagement between types of the learning environment and that learners are likely to engage in academics when they perceive their learning environment to be more autonomy-supportive than controlling (Espejo, 2018). Moreover, that when students see the school as a kind place, they are more motivated and interested in learning, resulting in a boost in their academic engagement (Datu& Park, 2019).

Learning performance predictors is a vital part of the learning process. Active participation or engagement is one such predictor, which has been widely analyzed in traditional learning settings, but less in the emerging social media-based learning environments (Mocanu, 2016). Preliminary exploratory information can help with a better understanding of what engages and motivates students for future studies (Daniel et al., 2017).

Transfer students are a distinct population. Their characteristics lead to different student experiences qualitatively. The students perceived their social and academic engagement, on the ways they engaged academically and socially and on how their perceptions of engagement and their actual patterns of engagement affected their sense of belonging (Lester, 2013). Academic performance or "academic achievement" is the degree to which a student, teacher, or institution has achieved their short or long-term educational goals.

At Misamis University, it has been observed that transfer students seem to have difficulty in their academic performance. Many of those students do not participate in some activities conducted in the school. They prefer to

watch than to actively participate in events. Even in the classroom setting, transfer students have this type of attitude in which teacher try to convince students to cooperate and to share their ideas. This study was conducted to know how transfer students cope with their new learning environment and the experiences they have.

II. METHODS

The respondents of this study were 269 transfer students in the Senior High School Department of Misamis University, Philippines. The respondents were transfer students with less than one year in the institution and did not attend their Junior High School in the academe. Thus, only transfer students coming from other schools were qualified to participate in this study. The respondents were given a questionnaire that investigated the transfer students' achievement goals, transfer students' engagement and academic performance of these transfer students.

The data were collected and analyzed using descriptive -correlational. Hence, this study is categorized as a descriptive qualitative study.

III. FINDINGS

A. Transfer Students' Achievement Goals

Table 1 presents the data on the achievement goals of the transfer students. It is shown that the achievement goals of the transfer students are good (M=3.06; SD=0.49). All the constructs such performance approach (M=3.16; SD=0.44), performance-avoidance approach (M=3.0; SD=0.49), mastery-avoidance approach (M=3.00; SD=0.49), and mastery approach (M=3.06; SD=0.53) are described good. This means that the students have positive orientations for how and why they engage in achievement situations. They have a good aim and motivation in their studies.

Constructs	M	SD	Interpretation
Performance Approach	3.16	0.44	Good
Performance-Avoidance Approach	3.0	0.49	Good
Mastery-Avoidance Approach	3.00	0.49	Good
Mastery Approach	3.06	0.53	Good
Overall Achievement Goals	3.06	0.49	Good

Table 1: Achievement Goals of the Transfer Students

Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (Very Good); 2.50-3.24 (Good); 1.75-2.49 (Fair); 1.0-1.74 (Poor)

B. Level of the Transfer Students' Engagement

Table 2 shows the data on the level of engagement of the transfer students. It is indicated that the transfer students' level of engagement had (M= 2.99; SD= 0.49), as supported by all constructs included such as agentic engagement

(M=2.56; SD=0.55), behavioural engagement (M=3.21, SD=0.50), emotional engagement (M=3.13; SD=0.45) and cognitive engagement (M=3.05; SD=0.43). This finding means that the students have a positive orientation toward any form of academic engagement.

Variable	M	SD	Interpretation
Agentic Engagement	2.56	0.55	Highly Engaged
Behavioral Engagement	3.21	0.50	Highly Engaged
Emotional Engagement	3.13	0.45	Highly Engaged
Cognitive Engagement	3.05	0.43	Highly Engaged
Overall Engagement	2.99	0.49	Highly Engaged

Table 2: Level of the Transfer Students' Engagement

Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (Very Highly Engaged); 2.50-3.24 (Highly Engaged); 1.75-2.49 (Fair); 1.0-1.74 (Poor)

C. Transfer Students' Academic Performance

Table 3 shows that academic performance of the transfer students was very satisfactory (M=86.65; SD= 5.07). The finding means that the transfer students performed well in

their academics. Despite being transfer students exposed to a new leaning environment, they were able to meet at desirable level the scholastic demands.

Grading Scale	M	SD
Outstanding	96	35.69
Very Satisfactory	77	28.62
Satisfactory	70	26.02
Fairly Satisfactory	26	9.67
Did Not Meet Expectation (below75)	-	-
Mean	86.65	Very Satisfactory

Table 3: Transfer Students' Academic Performance

Note: Grade Scale: 90-100 (Outstanding); 85-89 (Very satisfactory); 80-84 (Satisfactory); 75-79 (Fairly satisfactory); below75 (Did not meet expectations)

D. Significant Relationship between the Transfer Students' Achievement Goals and Academic Performance

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between transfer students' achievement as to mastery approach and

academic performance (r-value = 0.04; p-value =0.05). This finding implies that achievement goals affect the academic performance of the students. The goals or aims of the students can have an impact on their performance in school.

(n=269)			
Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Performance Approach & Performance	0.01	0.87	Not Significant
Performance-Avoidance Approach & Performance	0.09	0.15	Not Significant
Mastery-Avoidance Approach & Performance	0.04	0.50	Not Significant
Mastery Approach & Performance	0.04*	0.05	Significant

Table 4: Significant Relationship between the Transfer Students' Achievement Goals and Academic Performance

Note: * means significant at 0.05 level

E. Significant Relationship between the Transfer Students' Engagement and Academic Performance

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in determining the significant relationship between the transfer students' engagement and academic performance (Table 5). It is indicated that only agentic engagement and performance (r- value = 0.12; p-value=

0.04) are significantly related. This result means that agentic engagement affects the students' academic performance. Students frequently ask questions are able to attain understanding of the topics being discussed. Students formulate ideas not only to help oneself but also other students. Teachers gave high remarks for class participation to encourage other students to participate as well.

(n=269)			
Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Agentic Engagement & Performance	0.12*	0.04	Significant
Behavioral Engagement & Performance	0.08	0.17	Not Significant
Emotional Engagement & Performance	0.09	0.14	Not Significant
Cognitive Engagement & Performance	0.06	0.36	Not Significant

Table 5. Significant Relationship between the Transfer Students' Engagement and Academic Performance

Note: ** means highly significant at .01 level; * means significant at 0.05 level

F. Predictors of Transfer Students' Academic Performance

Table 6 shows that only one factor was found to be the predictor of the students' academic performance. This predictor is the agentic engagement ($\beta = 1.81$; $t = 2.06$, $p = 0.04$). Agentic engagement as the predictor means that the students ask frequent questions to better understand the topic discussed and thus, able to participate in the different events and activities in school.

Regression equation (Academic Performance= 92.06+ 1.81 engagement) indicates that the engagement of the teacher and students increases by a unit; the students' academic performance also increases by 92.06. The variation of the students is explained by engagement for only 50.43 percent since r^2 is 50.43. This result means that only 50.43 percent of the students' academic performance is attributed agentic engagement, while the remaining 49.57 percent is assigned to the other factors which are not included in the study.

(n=269)				
Predictors	Coef (β)	SE Coef	t- value	p-value
(Constant)	92.06	2.64	34.81	0.00
Agentic Engagement	1.81	0.88	2.06*	0.04

$R^2 = 50.43\%$
 Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
 Academic Performance = 92.06+1.81 Engagement

Table 6: Predictors of the Transfer Students' Academic Performance

Note: * means p-value ≤ 0.05 ; significant

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Achievement goal orientation affects learner's acts in terms of achievement and emotional, cognitive, and behavioristic reactions, not on learner's overall life goals. Learning orientation means learning work and getting an

expert in using personal standards and personal development. Learners with a high learning goal orientation try to develop their efficiency, learn new skills and subjects, and get experts in a new way of thinking and new concepts. A student who is learning goal-oriented focuses on

strategies helping to acquire knowledge and skills (Ozkal, 2013).

Students who perceived emphasis on mastery goals in the classroom use more effective strategies, preferred challenging tasks, had a more positive attitude toward the school, and had a stronger belief that success is a result of their efforts. Students who perceived performance goals as salient tended to focus on their ability and attributing failure to lack of knowledge. Students that listen attentively to the teachers' discussion have a great possibility of attaining good academic standing.

Students that able to participate in the class and voices out ideas had a significant impact on the teachers' performance. Hence, teachers able to improve the teaching technique to improve more the teaching instruction to enlighten more the students about the discussion taught. Teachers have to give class activities that require active participation from the students to understand well the topics at hand. Students can develop their skills better when they are given activities that can enhance their confidence to perform the assigned task to them. Students need to be heard to understand the essential role of engagement in the learning process.

Academic performance pertains to the rating or grade that the students get after the examination or quizzes. It is an assessment that enables the teacher to know where to reinforce the students if they got low scores. Different assessments help the students to excel well in their studies.

Achievement goals are found to influence students' learning outcomes. Goal achievement requires a committed, concentrated, and consistent work ethic to make your dreams a reality. The process of having goals helps clarify what the desire to do and understand the importance of pursuing and committing oneself to make things happen.

Academic achievement is essential to the successful development of young people in society. Students who do well in school are better able to make the transition into adulthood and to achieve occupational and economic success. Generally, academic success pertains to the student's self-motivation, self-efficiency, and ability to cope with the learning environment, with the only goal to achieve excellent academic performance at university or college.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The transfer students still manage to have desirable achievement goals as they respond to relevant situations in the new environment. Their act of being highly engaged in the school activities contributes to the attainment of very satisfactory performance in the class. The students' active engagement toward the teachers, desire to master new skills, and receive favorable judgment from other, have an impact on their performance in school. Agentic engagement has an influence on the scholastic achievement of the students.

Based on findings and conclusions, it is recommended that teachers give activities that are relevant to the students' mastery improvement. Using interactive, collaborative, and drill lessons allows learners to engage in the class activities to the maximum. Guidance counselors conduct seminars that help students in goal setting. Also, students give their best in academic undertakings. They may participate in the various activities provided by the teachers to build a good relationship with other students. Future researchers conduct further studies on how to improve the achievement goals of transfer students.

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